

Compost Toilets in Roskilde Festival

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INTRODUCTION

The Roskilde Festival is a major event in the Danish culture calendar. This year 100 000 persons will take part in the event: 25000 volunteers and 75000 visitors. For the first time a warming up period has been created and it adds 4 days to the 5 festival days. Thus, the camping area will be used during 9 days. The Roskilde festival organization developed the green footsteps campaign in order to reduce the ecological impact of the festival. This year, they created a lot of new ways of making the festival as eco friendly as possible but not in term of toilets. Since last year they used a 800m long line of traditional toilet boxes, we thought that there is a very important improvement to do by using composting toilets instead.

COMPOST TOILETS

Compost toilet designed by students from EverGreen Wash,USA

Composting toilets are toilet systems which treat human waste by composting and dehydration to produce a useable end-product that is a valuable soil additive. They come in a variety of models and brand names as well as different shapes and designs to enhance the natural composting process. They use little or no water, are not connected to expensive sewage systems, cause no environmental damage and produce a valuable resource for gardening.

This kind of toilets are more and more used in eco-friendly houses, but it still meets with a lot of false considerations.

WHY ROSKILDE FESTIVAL?

First of all, using this kind of toilets will considerably reduce the use of water and also the wastes due to the use of classic toilet box. Besides, the compost made will help to restore the land that will suffer from the festival.

And finally, it will make people realize that the compost toilets are an interesting alternative to the classic toilets that are one of the most water consuming source of our daily life.